

Developing Students' Moral Values in Elementary School: Using Moralizing, Modeling, and Guiding Methods

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ABSTRACT: Research on developing moral values has often been done and continues to this day. Although research on the topic has been done for a long time, continuous research needs to be done to get the right and accurate methods to foster students' moral values, especially at the elementary school level. This research aims to find out which method is better in fostering students' moral values in elementary schools. This study was a qualitative exploration in the case study genre. Data was collected from four elementary schools as a research unit. Two schools foster moral values through moralizing and modeling methods, while the others foster them by guiding. Data was collected using interview and observation techniques. Both methods are used to reveal differences in the impact of implementing moral value development methods. The data were analyzed using an interactive model developed by Miles, Huberman, and Saldana. This study found; (1) the guiding method is better for developing the moral values of primary school students compared to the moralizing and modeling methods; (2) The use of guiding methods in a strict and organized manner can better develop students' moral values; (3) implementation of the guiding method requires great effort to work optimally. The conclusion was that guiding is the best method for developing elementary school students' moral values, followed by moralizing and modeling.

KEYWORDS: moral values; elementary school; students; modeling; moralizing; guiding.

BACKGROUND

Research on developing moral values has often been done and continues to this day (Hanum & Suyata, Sumardi, 2020; Sumardi & Risprawati, 2020). Although research on the topic has been done for a long time, continuous research needs to be done to get the right and accurate methods to foster students' moral values, especially at the elementary school level. Theoretically, three approaches are commonly used in developing morals: the knowledge approach, the heart approach, and the environmental approach (Sumardi, 2021, pp. 137–140). According to Lickona, these approaches foster three moral domains: knowing, feeling, and action (Dalmeri, 2014). Moralizing and modeling are the two most applied methods in morals and behavior development (Sutama, Suranata, & Dharsana, 2014). In addition, the guiding technique is a helpful way to shape students' morale (Lickona, 1991, pp. 133). As Lickona (1991, pp. 549–550) described, moralizing is a means of growing students' morale by giving moral messages. This method emphasizes touching one's heart to be more aware of behaving according to values and norms. According to Gozali (Sumardi, 2021, pp. 78), moving someone's heart is a way to enhance individual morals. The modeling method forms morals through observing and generalizing other people's behavior to practice (Sutama, Suranata, & Dharsana, 2014). The emphasis of this method is to give examples of good behavior by grown individuals, especially those whom students see as role models. The exemplified behavior is imitated by students and is used as a pattern of their behavior in everyday life. It happens because children like to imitate other people's behaviors they idolize (Meltzoff & Williamson, 2017). As for guiding, when referring to Lickona's explanation (1991, pp. 132), it can be interpreted as assisting students by providing corrective feedback. This technique emphasizes giving children directions so they continue to behave according to moral rules.

As explained above, the methods of moral development are still insufficient for developing students' moral values, especially in the current disruptive era. Information and technological advancements significantly impact every aspect of life, including moral values. The findings of research conducted by Griffiths (2013), Zaremohzzabieh et al. (2014), and Sumardi, Risprawati, & Ismail (2017) showed that information technology causes a strong dependence on students. Information technology could cause dishonest behavior, a lack of responsibility, and laziness (Sumardi & Risprawati, 2020). Moreover, the negative impact of advances in information technology is far worse than the positive impact (Ngafifi, 2014). A more suitable method of moral development is needed to reduce its devastating negative effects. Therefore, it is necessary to find more compatible and better methods of moral

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development to develop students' moral values. Therefore, research on developing students' moral values needs to be conducted from time to time to find a better and more effective one.

To date, many studies have focused on finding and testing methods for developing students' moral values. Some of which are studies by Iplih (2017), Abdullah (2017), Ahmadi, Basuki, & Irawan (2020), Hanum, Suyata, & Sumardi (2020). Iplih (2017) at the boarding school Al-Mumtaz found many strategies to develop student moral values, including habituation, reward and punishment, modeling, and strict supervision. Meanwhile, Abdullah (2017), Islamic Middle School in West Java, believed that students moral values would enhance if they were grown and developed in a good culture and had good moral role models. Likewise, Ahmadi, Basuki, & Irawan (2020) showed several methods used by universities in East Java to grow student values and attitudes: modeling, habituation, intervention, and reinforcement. Meanwhile, the research findings conducted by Hanum, Suyata, and Sumardi (2020) at various universities in Mataram showed that value internalization could be implemented using two approaches: the partial and integral approaches. The good internalization methods used in both approaches are moralizing, intervention, and establishing a good culture. As elaborated above, studies focusing on finding the best student moral development approach are still insufficient. Research and trials on various methods of moral development are continuously conducted. The methods of moralizing, modeling, reward, and punishment are not the final ways to develop morality and cannot yet solve moral problems. In Indonesia, moral enhancement has been the main focus of education (Sumardi, 2012), and it has become more critical due to the disruption era. Prioritizing moral enhancement through education is reflected in the Indonesian national education curriculum, which places the domain of attitude as national education's first and foremost goal (Supardi, 2012). On the other hand, the progress of information technology, besides having a positive impact, has also disrupted various sectors, including moral disruption. Studies show that information technology's adverse effects are far greater than the benefits provided (Ngafifi, 2014; Sumardi & Rispawati, 2020). Based on these arguments, it is intended to find better and more accurate ways of developing students' moral values through explorative research to determine the accuracy of these modeling, moralizing, and guiding methods in developing their moral values.

As described above, the guiding method shapes students' moral values by providing suggestions and correcting attitudes and behavior (Lickona, 1991, pp. 132). The word "guiding" in the Merriam-Webster and Cambridge Dictionary means to show, supervise, or influence someone to do something in a certain way. In Vygotsky's lens (Chairani, 2015), guiding is the same as scaffolding, assisting children in learning or helping them perform specific actions they cannot do themselves. In this study, guiding refers to developing children's morals by explaining, exemplifying, and helping them behave according to the values and norms. In the view of Fraenkel (in Sumardi & Rispawati, 2020) and Lickona (1991, pp. 142), the configuration of a person's attitude is reflected in his behavior since good behavior represents a good attitude and vice versa.

In guiding methods, moral development is achieved through moralizing, modeling, and guiding students' behavior that agrees with values and norms. These are together activities with one momentum. In its application, guiding is to lead students in behaving based on values and norms. Guiding is giving moral messages and exemplifying and directing them on how they should behave. In this guiding process, adults teach moral messages, show how to behave, and direct students to behave according to what is ordered and exemplified. Based on the explanation above, three efforts are made to shape the students' moral values: giving moral messages, giving examples, and directing them to behave according to examples. These three activities are performed sequentially at one time. So, in terms of treatment, the guiding method is more directed, intense, and has a clear orientation toward shaping students' moral values. Theoretically, the guide intensity and action determine the impact of the changes. The more intense and comprehensive the guidance is, the greater the outcomes; the more intense the stimulus, the stronger the urge to behave as expected (Coskun, 2019). All in all, through guiding method treatment, this method has a clearer motivation for developing students' moral values than the other two methods. With a stronger driving force, it can be hypothesized that the guiding method is more effective in developing students' moral values.

Regarding students' moral development, it can be explained by Piaget and Kohlberg's moral development theory. According to Piaget (Nucci, Narvaez, & Krettenauer, 2014), moral development occurs in two stages: heteronomous morality (4–10 years) and autonomous morality (10 years and over). Heteronomous morality is the stage of moral development in which students behave well or comply with norms when forced. The force can be through punishment or reward. This moral development occurs in the same direction as in others. Autonomous morality is a stage of moral development in which students' behavior is based on their awareness (Carlos & Costa, 2019). Meanwhile, according to Kohlberg (Syafrihsyah, Yusoff, & Othman, 2017), the stages are categorized into three: pre-conventional (0–10 years), conventional (10–12 years), and post-conventional (12 years and over). The characteristics of the pre-conventional level are oriented toward punishment, obedience, and instrumental relativism. The characteristics of the conventional level are a good boy-good girl and law-and-order-oriented. While the characteristics of the post-conventional level are oriented to the social contract and universal ethical principles (Slavin, 2000, pp. 55). Based on these opinions, the moral development stages of the research subject are included in heteronomous morality/pre-conventional. The characteristic of students at this stage is that they will take certain moral actions based on consequences (Slavin, 2000, pp. 53; Nainggolan & Naibaho, 2022).

Students moral values would be seen in their emerging behavior during the research. Since moral attitude is an abstract concept, it cannot be observed directly (Sumardi, Rispawati, and Ismail, 2017). One of the most accurate ways to get a picture of changes in a person's moral values is to observe their moral actions (words and actions) (Fraenkel in Sumardi & Rispawati, 2020). What a person

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says and does is a reflection of the students' values and attitudes (Wahyudiati et al., 2020; Wahyudiati, Sutrisno, & Supiah, 2019). Therefore, this study indicated changes in students' moral values through changes in their behavior in words and actions. Based on the description above, this research explored how to better educate moral values in elementary students. The focus of this research is students' respectful and responsible attitudes. These two characters represent the main morality that applies universally (Lickona, 1991, pp. 69). Respect is believing that other people are valuable mans (Fredman, 2018, pp. 3). Meanwhile, responsibility is a person's obligation to carry out appropriately what is required (Widyanti et al., 2020, pp. 26). Respect will be seen in several indicators, as stated by Samani and Hariyanto (2012, pp. 128): being polite, not insulting other people, saying thank you, and apologizing easily. The attitude of responsibility will be seen in several indicators, namely, students' readiness to participate in learning, initiative to actively participate in learning, and completing assignments on time (Aisyah et al., 2014; Kartika et al., 2016, pp. 8; Widyanti et al., 2020, pp. 26).

METHOD

This research adopted a qualitative approach to exploring research problems. According to Bogdan and Taylor (Moleong, 2006, pp. 4), naturalistic research produces descriptive data as a narrative. The use of a naturalistic approach was based on the research setting and the type of data collected. The setting was natural; the activities are oriented towards the moral development of the research subject, namely, respect and responsibility. This research unit was a neutral elementary school consisting of the State Elementary School (SDN) 44 Mataram, SDN 45 Mataram (Unit-1 Group), SDN 3 Merembu, and the Integrated Islamic Elementary School (SDIT) Muslim Cendikia (Unit-2 Group). The SDN 44 and SDN 45 Mataram develop students' moral values by moralizing and modeling, while the SDN 33 Merembu and SDIT Muslim Cendikia instill students' moral values by guiding. The data type was qualitative in the form of a description of the development of respect and the responsibilities of the research subject, which was developed through modeling, moralizing, and guiding methods. The data on the moral development of the research subjects was explored in depth to get a complete picture of how effectively these methods shape students' moral values. The SDN 44 and 45 Mataram has been implementing moralizing and modeling, whereas the SDN 3 Merembu and SDIT Muslim Cendikia has been implementing guidance. Two contexts for applying those methods were respect (C1) and responsibility (C2). Respect can be shown through words and actions, while responsibility is proven through actions and the product.

The subjects of this research were elementary school students in grades 1 to 6 from both elementary schools. Data were collected using interview and observation techniques. Both methods are used to collect data about students' moral qualities. Interview data was taken with the help of interview guidelines and electronic recording. As for the observed data, it was recorded in the observation memo. Through this technique, the daily behavior changes could be completely noted. Then, the data were analyzed using interactive model analysis techniques, as stated by Miles, Huberman, & Saldana (2014, pp. 8), which consist of three stages: data condensation, data presentation, and concluding. Data condensation was done by abstracting the data from the observation memo and transferring it to the research findings data table. The research findings data table was formatted according to the number and sequence of methods applied. Data display was performed by combining narrative presentation techniques with tables or research findings data tables. With the data display technique, the data could be described entirely and easily understood. The conclusion was drawn by generalizing the research findings based on the discussion.

FINDINGS

The data in this study were collected by interviewing and observing the research subject (students). Students moral values can be seen in three aspects: speech, action, and product. These three aspects are categorized into two types of morality, namely, moral saying and moral action. Based on the data collection techniques above, the data obtained is as stated in the table below.

Table 1. Research Data

No	Research Unit	Method	Context	Findings
1	Unit-1 Group	Modeling and Moralizing	C1	Many students speak rudely, say dirty words, and bully their friends. Many students behave impolitely. Students rarely express gratitude to others. There were no students who apologized when they made a mistake.
			C2	Many students didn't bring learning tools and didn't study the material before coming to school. Student participation during the learning process is low. Only a few students have the initiative to be actively involved in learning. Many of them didn't complete their homework, and they didn't do it as ordered.

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2	Unit-2 Group	Guiding	C1	<p>At the SDIT Muslim Cendikia, there were no students who spoke rudely, said dirty, and bullied their friends. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, there are students who speak harshly, bully their friends, and even threaten them.</p> <p>At the SDIT Muslim Cendikia, there were no students who behaved inappropriately. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, several students were found behaving impolitely.</p> <p>At the SDIT Muslim Cendikia, students seem to be used to saying thank you to other people. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, it was found that students were not used to expressing it. It was found that only a few students expressed their thanks to others.</p> <p>At the SDIT Muslim Cendikia, it was found that students were accustomed to apologizing when they felt guilty. As for SDN 3 Merembu, it is difficult to find students who apologize. They are not used to apologizing when they make a mistake.</p>
			C2	<p>At SDIT Muslim Cendikian, all students equip themselves with the tools needed for learning. At SDN 3 Merembu, there were students who did not bring their learning equipment. At SDIT Muslim Cendikia, students are accustomed to studying the material before coming to school. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, several students didn't do it.</p> <p>At the SDIT Muslim Cendikia, the level of student participation in learning is very high. Almost all students have the initiative to be involved in learning. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, there are some students who are less active in learning. They lack the initiative to be actively involved in learning.</p> <p>At SDIT Muslim Cendikia, there are almost no students who do not complete their homework. Students collect assignments on time and complete them as requested. Meanwhile, at SDN 3 Merembu, there are still students who do not complete their homework. They formulate their homework as directed.</p>

Based on the data in the table above, it is known that in elementary schools that use moralizing and modeling methods to instill students' moral values, many students have poor respect and responsibility. Students' poor respect can be seen from their lack of manners, actions that degrade others, difficulty apologizing when they are wrong, and rarely thanking others for their good deeds. Meanwhile, students' lack of responsibility was evident in the number of students who were unprepared for the lesson, low participation during the lesson, and the fact that many students did not complete their assignments properly.

In contrast to students in elementary schools that use guiding methods to foster students' moral values, they have high respect. In the school that strictly applies the method (SDIT Muslim Cendikia), the students are very respectful. Their words and actions are polite, they do not disrespect others, they always say thank you for the kindness of others, and they are used to apologizing if they make mistakes. As for the school that applies the guiding method more loosely (SDN 3 Merembu), the students' respect is not as good as in the primary school that applies the method strictly. However, their respect is better than that of students in schools that apply moralizing and modeling methods.

Likewise, with responsibility, the elementary schools that apply the guiding method have students with a high level of responsibility. They are well prepared for learning, active in the learning process, and complete tasks well. In this aspect, students have a different quality of responsibility between schools that apply the guiding method strictly and schools that are lax. Students in schools that use the guiding method strictly have a higher level of responsibility than those that do not apply the method loosely.

DISCUSSION

From the description of the research data above, several findings were obtained related to the implementation of modeling, moralizing, and guiding methods in developing students' moral values, namely: 1) the guiding method is better or more effective in fostering the moral values of elementary school students; 2) the guiding method applied in a stricter and more organized way is much better or more effective in fostering the moral values of students. Both research findings can be explained as described below. First, the research findings that show that the modeling method is better or more effective in fostering students' moral values compared to the moralizing and modeling methods prove that the guiding method has strong power in internalizing moral values. On the other hand, the moralizing and modeling methods do not have sufficient power to develop students' moral values. Based on

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motivation theory, the impetus that can change a person is an action that can cause awareness. This means that a person will behave in a certain way if he realizes that he feels important or needs to do it (Dasler in Adjarwati, 2015). Therefore, the inability of moralizing and modeling methods to shape students' moral values is due to the limited ability of these methods to raise students' awareness. The modeling method cannot stimulate and excite students to behave as expected. This is due to the absence of strict and organized intervention from the method.

In addition, through the view of Piaget's moral development theory (Nucci, Narvaez, & Krettenauer, 2014; Carlos & Costa, 2019) and Kohlberg (Slavin, 2000, pp. 55; Syafrilsyah, Yusoff, & Othman, 2017), children at the age of 2-12 years are still at the heteronomous/pre-conventional stage of morality development. One of the characteristics of this stage of moral development is that children will perform certain moral actions based on coercion or stimulus from others (Nainggolan & Naibaho, 2022). Based on the two theories above, it is clear that strict and organized interventions are needed to make elementary school students have good moral values.

So, it is clear that the inability of the moralizing and modeling methods to develop moral values is caused by two conditions: the poor ability of the methods to motivate children to behave in certain moral ways and the incompatibility of these methods with the stages of students' moral development. The compatibility of this method is reflected in the characteristics of the moralizing and modeling methods, where these methods only provide suggestions and examples and only rely on a student's sensitivity and awareness.

Second, guiding methods that are applied in a strict and organized manner have a better or more effective impact on fostering students' moral values. Strict and organized implementation of the guiding method means applying the method optimally. The optimal implementation of the guiding method definitely has an impact on the quality of students' moral values. This is because the creative power of the method becomes stronger. The greater the creative power produced, the faster the change in moral values will occur in students. In addition, the guiding method is a method that has a greater number of interventions compared to other methods. In the guiding method, there are three methods that are applied simultaneously, namely moralizing, modeling, and directing. Therefore, the guiding method is better in fostering students' moral values.

In addition, the guiding method, which is strictly implemented and organized, will create an environment that supports the development of students' moral values. Implementation in this way for a long time will create a school culture that can foster students' moral values better. The findings of this study are in line with empiricism theory, which explains that environmental factors influence a person's knowledge and actions. The environment is the main source of knowledge and truth (Sativa, 2011). This theory is reinforced by research conducted by Fitri and Na'imah (2020) and Boros, Apostu, & Vasile (2020), which shows social and environmental factors affect a person's moral behavior. Environmental factors are the dominant factors that influence children's moral values (Uzoka & Njoku, 2015). In addition, the results of this study are in line with DePorter's opinion (Zahran, 2019), which states that children learn faster from a comfortable environment and from what they see and do. The research findings prove that the intensity of intervention from others determines whether children learn more. Based on its characteristics, the guiding method is a method in which there is a moralization method and an exemplary method that has a more intense level of intervention than other methods. Therefore, it is logical that the guiding method is more effective in developing children's moral actions than the moralizing and modeling methods.

Third, the findings of this study confirm that moral development using the guiding method requires more effort than the moralizing and modeling methods. The effort in this study is referred to as an intervention. In the modeling method, the intervention is not done directly or even unintentionally. The first condition, the model behaving well, may not be intended for students to imitate or behave as the model does. In the second condition, the model behaves with the intention that students imitate the modeled action. Interventions like this are categorized as passive interventions. Whereas in the moralizing and modeling method, the intervention is done intentionally and directly. Moral messages, corrections, directions, and examples are done intentionally and are intended for children to behave in accordance with values and norms. This is called active intervention. The difference between interventions in moralizing and modeling methods lies in the level of intervention. Intervention in the moralizing method is still limited; students are only told to behave in accordance with values and norms. While the modeling method not only gives messages and examples but also guides students to behave in accordance with the norms.

Thus, the intervention provided by the modeling method is very intensive. With a high level of intervention, it is natural that this method has the strongest influence on the development of students' moral values compared to other methods. This is in accordance with the opinion of Sunil & Verma (2018) and Asy'ary (2019) who state that the treatment given to children is very influential on their development, especially on their morals. The results of research conducted by Ludova & Lasek (2014) also prove that the education model given to students has a crucial impact on their moral development. The effects are not only momentary but also felt continuously (Pentiernitasari & Eliza, 2021).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion of the research findings above, it can be concluded that several things are related to the problem under study, namely:

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1. The guiding method is better in developing moral values of elementary school students than the moralizing and modeling methods. Schools should use the guiding method to foster students' moral values because this method is better than others.
2. The guiding method that is applied in a strict and organized manner can develop students' moral values well. The more rigorous and organized the moral values coaching is done by the school, the better the students' moral values will develop. Therefore, schools must apply these methods in a strict and organized manner so that students' moral values develop optimally.
3. It takes hard work and organized efforts from schools to be able to produce good student moral values. To be able to implement the guiding method properly, the school must equalize the vision and mission of all school communities.

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LS drafted the article. AF reviews and revises the article.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Data is available, and a link can be provided to a Google Drive folder containing the data if necessary.

DISCLAIMER

The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of any affiliated agency of the author.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdullah, D. (2017). Internalization Prosocial Value by Exemplary in Building Nation Character in School. Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Sociology Education (ICSE 2017), 1, 247-258.
- 2) Adjarwati, T. (2015). Motivation in Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, Herzberg's Two Factor Theory, McGregor's X Y Theory, and McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory. *Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi & Manajemen*, 1(1), 45-54.
- 3) Ahmadi, Basuki, & Irawan, E. (2020). The Internalization of Attitude and Values: Comparison Study in PTKIN and PTKIS. *Cendekia*, 8(1), 17-32.
- 4) Aisyah, A., Nusantoro, E., & Kurniawan, K. (2014). Increase Learning Responsibilities through Content Usage Services. *Indonesian Journal of Guidance and Counseling: Theory and Application*, 3(3), 44-50.
- 5) Asy'ary. S. (2019). Violence Against Children. *Jurnal Keislaman*, 2(2), 178-194.
- 6) Boros, A., Apostu, S. A., & Vasile, V. (2020). Factors Influencing Morality. "Ovidius" University Annals, Economic Sciences Series, 20(2), 235-239.
- 7) Cambridge Dictionary, Retrieved from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/guiding>.
- 8) Carlos, A. & Costa, R. (2019). An Agent-oriented Account of Piaget's Theory of Interactional Morality. *AI & SOCIETY*, 34(3), 649-676. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-018-0804-1>.
- 9) Coskun, K. (2019). Conditioning Tendency among Preschool and Primary School Children: Cross-Sectional Research. *Interchange*, 50, 517-536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10780-019-09373-1>.
- 10) Dalmeri (2014). Education for Character Development (A Study of Thomas Lickona's Ideas in Educating for Character). *Al-Ulum*, 14(1), 269-288.
- 11) Fitri, M. & Na'imah (2020). Factors Influencing Moral Development in Early Childhood. *Al Athfaal: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 3(1), 1-15.
- 12) Friedman, C. (2018). RESPECT: The Relationship between Being Respected and Quality of Life of Disabled People. *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 38(2).78-86.
- 13) Griffiths, M. D. (2013). Social Networking Addiction: Emerging Themes and Issue. *Addiction Research & Therapy*, 4(5), 1-8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2155-6105.1000e118>.

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- 14) Hanum, F., Suyata, & Sumardi, L. (2020). A Better Approach to Internalizing Nationalism in Higher Education. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 13(11), 182-197.
- 15) Iplih, M. (2017). The Strategy of Internalizing the Values of the Characters in Al-Mumtaz Islamic Boarding School. *Attarbiyah: Journal of Islamic Culture and Education*, 2(1), 79-103. <https://doi.org/10.18326/attarbiyah.v2i1.79-103>.
- 16) Kartika, L., Tandililing, E., & Bistari. (2016). Application of Engaged Learning Strategy in Developing Learning Responsibility and Mathematical Connection Abilities of High School Students. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Khatulistiwa*, 5(4), 21-30.
- 17) Ludova, I. & Lasek, J. (2014). Parenting Style and Its Influence on the Personal and Moral Development of the Child. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 174, 1247-1254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.744>.
- 18) Meltzoff, A. N. & Williamson, R. A. (2017). Imitation and Modeling', Reference Module in Neuroscience Biobehavioral Psychology. December, 1-10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-809324-5.05827-2>.
- 19) Merriam-Webster Dictionary, Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/guide>.
- 20) Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Method Sourcebook*. SAGE Publication, Inc.
- 21) Moleong, L. J. (2006). *Qualitative Research Methodolog*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 22) Nainggolan, M. M. & Naibaho, L. (2022). 'The Integration of Kohlberg Moral Development Theory with Education Character. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 31, 203-212.
- 23) Ngafifi, M. (2014). Technological Advances and Patterns of Human Life in the Socio-Cultural Perspective. *Jurnal Pembangunan Pendidikan: Fondasi dan Aplikasi*, 2(1), 33-47.
- 24) Nucci, L., Narvaez, D., & Krettenauer, T. (2014). *Handbook of Moral and Character Education (Second Edition)*. New York and London: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- 25) Pentiermitasari, E. & Eliza, D. (2021). The efforts to Prevent Child Abuse. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 5(3), 9541-9546.
- 26) Samani, M. & Hariyanto. (2017). *Concept and Model: Character Education*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 27) Sativa. (2011). Emperism, an Architectural Research Approach. *INERSIA*, 7(2), 115-123.
- 28) Slavin, R. E. (2000). *Educational Psychology: Theory and Practice*. USA: Allyn & Bacon.
- 29) Sumardi, L. (2012). The Revitalization of Social Sciences Teaching in Elementary School as an Effort to Create Students Who Have Good Character. *Socia*, 11(2), 157-164.
- 30) Sumardi, L., Risprawati, & Ismail, M. (2017). The Effect of Information Technology on Learning (A Study on Civic and Pancasila Education Students at Mataram University). *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*, 24(2), 73-78.
- 31) Sumardi, L. & Risprawati. (2020). The Use of Internet in Learning and Its Impacts on Students' Moral Values: A Case Study in Mataram University, Indonesia. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(14), 790-794. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.14.142>.
- 32) Sumardi, L. (2021). *Pendidikan AntiKkorupsi [Anti-Corruption Education]*. Pustaka Lombok.
- 33) Sunil, S. & Verma, S. K. (2018). Moral Socialization: The Role of Parents. *IAHRW International Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), 165-170.
- 34) Supardi, U. S. (2012). The Direction of Education in Indonesia at the Policy and Implementation. *Jurnal Formatif*, 2(2): 111-121.
- 35) Sutama, G. A., Suranata, K., & Dharsana, K. (2014). The Implementation of Behavioral Theory Combined with Modeling Techniques to Increase the Learning Independence of AK C Class Students at the SMK 1 Singaraja. *Jurnal Ilmiah Bimbingan Konselin*, 2(1), 126-132.
- 36) Uzoka, N. R. & Njoku, U. (2015). Environmental Factors Influencing the Moral Behavior of Secondary School Students in Imo State, Nigeria. *International Scientific Conference "Rural Environment, Education, Personality, Jegava*, 05, 15-15.
- 37) Wahyudiati, D., Rohaeti, E., Irwanto, Wiyarsi, A., & Sumardi, L. (2020). Attitudes toward Chemistry, Self-Efficacy, and Learning Experiences of Pre-Service Chemistry Teachers: Grade Level and Gender Differences. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(1), 235-254. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.13116a>.
- 38) Wahyudiati, D., Sutrisno, H. & Louise, I. S. Y. (2019). Investigation of Attitudes toward Chemistry and Learning Experiences of Pre-Services Chemistry Teachers. *MIER Journal of Educational Studies, Trend & Practices*, 9(2), 191-211.
- 39) Widyanti, A., Hasudungan, S., & Park, J. (2020). E-learning Readiness and Perceived Learning Workload Among Students in an Indonesian University. *Knowledge Management & Elearning: An International Journal*, 12(1), 18-29.
- 40) Zahran, M. (2019). Quantum Learning: Specifications, Principles, and Factors that Influence It. *JRTIE: Journal of Research and Thought of Islamic Education*, 2(2), 141-157.
- 41) Zaremohzzabieh, et al. (2014). Addictive Facebook Use among University Students. *Asian Social Science*, 10(6), 107-116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ass.v10n6p107>.